

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE FORMATION OF AESTHETIC CULTURE IN YOUTH

Suvanova Dilnura Kurbanovna

Assistant of the Department of Social and Humanities, Physical Culture and Sports,
Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine University of Animal Husbandry and
Biotechnology

Narzieva Nargiza Norkuzievna

Head of the Department of Social and Humanities, Physical Culture and Sports of
Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and
Biotechnology, associate professor

Sultanova Ozoda Rajabovna

Assistant of the Department of Social and Humanities, Physical Culture and Sports,
Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and
Biotechnology

Abstract. The article analyzes the question of aesthetic culture, its place in the life of society and the factors affecting it. The influence of aesthetic culture on the social activity and intellectual level of young people is considered. The role and importance of aesthetic consciousness and culture in human spiritual development and the social and philosophical issues of the factors affecting it are expressed.

Key words: Aesthetic culture, social life, aesthetic consciousness, aesthetic activity, factors influencing it, social activity of young people, aesthetic culture and social activity, spiritual maturity of a person.

The establishment of a democratic legal state and civil society in Uzbekistan, rapid development in all spheres of social life, and the success of reforms depend on the level of social activity, intellectual knowledge, and aesthetic culture of young people. can make his due contribution. Today, increasing the social activity of young people, raising their spirituality, acquisition of worldly knowledge by them, formation of the skill of efficient use of advanced technologies, raising the level of aesthetic consciousness and culture are issues that are gaining urgent importance.

Fundamental changes in our country put the further development of the state policy on youth on the agenda, - says President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, - it is necessary to develop uniform indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of work with youth, and introduce a national index for evaluating youth policy. The Youth Union of Uzbekistan should develop the concept "Youth of Uzbekistan - 2025", in which practical measures to raise a mentally and physically mature generation should be determined.

Aesthetic knowledge creates deep and stable aesthetic interests. Aesthetic knowledge among young people prepares them to be aesthetic activists and to express their activities. Man tries to change the environment based on the laws of beauty, to create beauty. In this process, a number of factors directly affect it. An aesthetically educated person strives to make life beautiful, tries to be aesthetically active. The aesthetic activity of a person is manifested in the following factors, activities aimed at creating beauty in life, beautiful and elegant clothing, cultural behavior, self-control, creating an aesthetic environment in the family and work. A number of factors influence the process of acquiring theoretical and practical aesthetic knowledge, such

as the formation of aesthetic knowledge in young people, education of aesthetic culture, awareness of examples of aesthetic and cultural heritage, development of aesthetic feeling, social life of young people, it consists of feeling the beauty of nature and work, developing the need to strive for beauty, forming an aesthetic ideal, thinking, acting, and striving to be beautiful in appearance. The aesthetic culture of young people is reflected in their aesthetic feeling, knowledge, worldview. Aesthetic culture expresses society's attitude to art, beauty and aesthetic values. The aesthetic culture of society includes its interest in art, the ability to appreciate works of art, respect for aesthetic values, and the perception of beauty. Aesthetic culture is an indicator of the cultural wealth and artistic skills of society. The aesthetic ethos of a society is expressed through works of art and architectural structures that reflect its values, beliefs and style. Development and preservation of the aesthetic mentality of the society serves its cultural and social development. Aesthetic civilization creates an environment that arouses interest in art and artistic production in society and serves to educate young people as well-rounded people.

The development of aesthetic culture increases activity in a person, encourages him to try and realize his creative potential. Such a socio-historical and morally necessary issue - the study of the formation and development of aesthetic culture in society is considered relevant both theoretically and practically. The level of education and the fact that the aesthetic culture and the need for it in the society are constantly increasing in the process of social development are an objective process that is taking place in the changes in the spiritual and cultural spheres. As a result, the national and universal values that serve the development of the aesthetic culture of the individual in the society, including the research of the spiritual heritage of our ancestors, the scientific-theoretical study of reality based on their achievements, and the theoretical-methodological issues aimed at creating a system that represents the interests of the people become important.

As noted in the monograph of Otabek Gaybullayev called "Esthetic culture", "The formation and development of aesthetic culture is an important factor in determining the spiritual image of young people and their formation as a socially active person. have".

Aesthetic culture forms feelings of love for the Motherland and loyalty to the country in the worldview of the individual, especially the young generation. The issue of educating a physically strong, morally clean, aesthetically cultured, spiritually mature generation in society is considered a priority task in state policy. On this basis, significant work is being carried out to strengthen the civic position and activity of our young generation, to educate them as independent thinkers, well-rounded individuals who can compete in the international arena, mastering modern knowledge and skills, - says Shavkat Mirziyoyev, - Most importantly, young people the task of maintaining constant communication with them, ensuring their employment, finding their place in life, becoming worthy members of society, and improving their working and living conditions is becoming a criterion of all of our daily activities.

On September 14, 2016, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Policy Regarding Youth" No. ORQ-406 was adopted, and Article 12/1 of this law

states that "Powers of cultural bodies in the field of state policy regarding youth" named This article states, "Cultural bodies: support creative youth in every way, create necessary conditions for them to fully demonstrate their talents and abilities."

National aesthetic culture is considered to be a factor that nurtures high spirituality through its unique influence on the heart and mind of a person. Aesthetic culture helps to acquire and implement universal spiritual values. Creative use of historical and artistic traditions creates an opportunity to master the laws of their gradual development. It ensures the interaction of national culture with the cultures of other nations, harmony with the goals and interests of the national idea. Works of art, as well as the development of modern life and folk aesthetics, create an opportunity to use the achievements of technical aesthetics in the development of industrial products. Forms an uncompromising critical attitude to works of art, healthy aesthetic taste and needs. At the same time, social and spiritual factors such as school education, higher education, extracurricular institutions, youth clubs, music schools have a unique influence on the development of aesthetic culture.

Aesthetic culture is manifested through the aesthetics of professional activity. Aesthetics of professional activity refers to learning and teaching the owners of any profession to organize their service activities based on the laws, principles, and tools of sophistication through an aesthetic attitude to reality. The aesthetics of professional activity performs the following tasks: 1) to help its employees create, change and reconstruct the world based on the laws of beauty; 2) to be able to distinguish beauty, heroism and grandeur from their antipode, ugliness, cowardice and meanness; 3) organization of aesthetic education based on the laws and principles of sophistication.

On January 28, 2022, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev No. PF-60 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" was adopted, and in Appendix 1 to this decree, citizens, first of all great attention was paid to the issue of improving the aesthetic culture of young people. In the 75th goal of the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan, attention is focused on the issue of "Development of fine and applied art and design directions, raising the artistic and aesthetic taste of the population", and in the 76th goal, "Culture and art spheres" further development, improvement of the material and technical base of cultural institutions and objects" was paid attention to.

On September 11, 2023, the Decree No. PF-158 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy was adopted, and the 1st goal in Appendix 1 to the decree, "To give each person his potential creating suitable conditions for its realization". Direction 1.5 of this goal is called "Reforms to ensure spiritual development and bring the cultural sector to a new level", and goal 42 in the annex to the decree "Protection of cultural heritage, scientific study" and further improvement of activities related to popularization". In this direction, "Transformation of more than 3,000 archival materials in the archives of the Institute of Art Studies, Institute of Uzbek Language, Literature and Folklore into a modern format, achieve the inclusion of at least 3 unique examples of intangible cultural heritage in the international lists of UNESCO, more than 30 tasks

such as in-depth scientific research of intangible cultural heritage elements, preservation of 158 cultural heritage objects were defined.

It is necessary to establish new cultural and recreational parks on the basis of public-private partnership, and to take measures to turn them into modern youth centers, - says President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, - These parks primarily include sports fields, amphitheater and small stages, libraries, There should be "book cafes".

Today in Uzbekistan, a lot of attention is paid to the issue of raising a mature generation, raising young people to be people with a broad worldview, thorough acquisition of various knowledge, good knowledge of foreign languages, computer technologies, aesthetic, cultural, ethical, political, legal, economic consciousness and culture. great attention is paid to the issue. At the same time, great attention is paid to the issue of the cultural level of a person, his aesthetic consciousness and culture as an important criterion of human perfection. The cultural level of a person, his aesthetic consciousness and culture are important in the formation of the nation's gene pool, and will serve to ensure the great future of Uzbekistan in the future. Civilization of citizens, especially young people, high level of aesthetic consciousness and aesthetic culture is determined by their healthy, intelligent, enlightened, humane, hardworking, responsible. Aesthetic culture and aesthetic education as important factors of human spiritual development are important in social development.

REFERENCES USED

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. O'zbekiston yoshlariga bayram tabrigi // Milliy tiklanishdan – milliy yuksalish sari. 4-jild, Toshkent, O'zbekiston, 2020 yil.
2. G'aybullayev Otabek. Estetik madaniyat. Monografiya. Toshkent, Navro'z nashriyoti, 2020 yil.
3. Faybulayev Otabek. Эстетик маданият. Монография. Тошкент, "Chashma print" nashriyoti, 2008 йил.
4. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. O'zbekiston yoshlariga bayram tabrigi // Xalqimizning roziligi bizning faoliyatimizga berilgan eng oliy bahodir. 2-jild, Toshkent, O'zbekiston, 2018 yil.
5. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni. "Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to'g'risida". 2016 yil 14-sentyabr, O'RQ-406-son. <https://lex.uz/docs/3026246>
6. Yaxshilikov J.Ya., Muhammadiyev N.E. Falsafa. Darslik. Samarqand, 2021yil.
7. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni. "2022-2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida". 2022 yil 28-yanvar, №PF-60. <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>
8. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni. 2023 yil, 11 sentyabr №PF-158. "O'zbekiston-2030" strategiyasi to'g'risida. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6600413>
9. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Oliy Majlisga murojaatnomasi // Niyati ulug' xalqning ishi ham ulug', hayoti yorug' va kelajagi farovon bo'ladi. 3-jild, Toshkent, O'zbekiston, 2019 yil.
10. Mustafakulovich, K. S., & Kurbanovna, S. D. (2023). Effect of Aesthetic Categories on Human Spirituality. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(11), 501-503.

11. Rajabovna, S. O. (2023, December). OLIY O 'QUV YURTLARIDA TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING O 'RNI. In *INTERDISCIPLINE INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 391-393).
12. Rajabovna, S. O. (2023, December). TALABA YOSHLARNI O 'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO 'LLASH. In *INTERDISCIPLINE INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 389-390).
13. Kurbanovna, S. D., & Mustafakulovich, K. S. (2022). The Role of Aesthetic Culture in Educational Processes. *Open Access Repository*, 8(04), 208-210.
14. Vahabov, M. T., Jamolov, L. U., Turgunboev, O., & Suvonova, D. K. (2022). Key Issues of Development Strategy and Educational Propagation of the New Uzbekistan. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES*, 3(11), 101-109.
15. Kurbanovna, S. D. (2023). GO'ZALIK VA ULUGVORLIK KATEGORIYALARINING IJTIMOY-FALSAFIY TAHLILI. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 3(10), 96-98.
16. Suvanova, D. (2023). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THE SIGNIFICANCE OF RELIGIOUS VALUES IN THE FORMATION OF AESTHETIC CULTURE AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 3(1 Part 1), 108-115.
17. Суванова, Д. К. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ У МОЛОДЕЖИ. In *История, современное состояние и перспективы инновационного развития науки* (pp. 86-88).
18. Суванова, Д. К. (2020). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО СОЗНАНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ. In *Научные исследования: проблемы и перспективы* (pp. 206-210).
19. Suvanova, D., & Karoboyev, S. (2023). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF RELIGIOUS VALUES IN FORMING AESTHETIC CULTURE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(26), 103-108.
20. Kurbanovna, S. D. (2023). YOSHLARDA ESTETIK MADANIYAT SHAKLLANISHINING METODOLOGIK MASALALARI. *FINLAND" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS"*, 14(1).
21. Sultanova, O., & Sadullayev, S. (2024). APPLICATION OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION OF STUDENTS. *Science and innovation*, 3(B2), 431-433.
22. Sultonova, O. (2022). QISHLOQ YOSHLARINING IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY AHVOLI VA UNI YAXSHILASH YO'LLARI. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(2), 127-130.
23. Rajabovna, S. O. (2023). THE PLACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN YOUTH EDUCATION. *Academia Science Repository*, 4(04), 85-89.

24. Нарзиева, Н. Н. (2019). Умумтаълим мактаб ўқувчиларида таянч компетенциялар асосида тадқиқотчилик кўникмаларини шакллантириш: пед. фан...(PhD) дисс.

25. Narzieva, N. (2017). Development of Education And Research Activity Profile Class Students on The Basis of Integrative And Personal Approach. *www.auris-verlag.de*.

26. Narzieva, N. N. (2019). Formation of research skills in general education school students based on basic competencies: ped. science...(PhD) diss. *Samarkand: SamDU*.

27. Norkuzievna, N. N., & Solieva, S. G. (2022). Formation of Students' Research Skills in the Process of English Lessons. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 8, 141-143.

28. Norkuzievna, N. N., & Solieva, S. G. (2022, March). DEVELOPING RESEARCH SKILLS ON THE BASIS OF COMPETENT APPROACH TO STUDENTS IN AN INTEGRATED LEARNING CONDITION. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 151-154).

29. Norkuzievna, N. N. (2022). Development Of Research Competences Of Future Veterinary Specialists In The Process Of Lessons. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 15, 41-43.

30. Turgunboev, A., & Narzieva, N. N. (2022). Zoroastrianism's source of education-interpretation of veterinary and animal husbandry in" Avesta. *Scientific Journal of Agrobiotechnology and Veterinary Medicine*, ps, 1180-1183.

31. Hasanovna, S. K., & Nargiza, N. (2019). The advantages of teaching grammar through games. *Достижения науки и образования*, (6 (47)), 30-31.

32. Khusenova, N. I., Fayzieva, F. N., Narzieva, N. N., & Rajabova, G. R. (2019). THE CONTENT OF TEACHING LISTENING IN ENGLISH AT ELEMENTARY SCHOOL. In *EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY* (pp. 45-47).

33. Нарзиева, Н. (2017). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ У УЧАЩИХСЯ НА ОСНОВЕ ИНТЕГРАТИВНОГО ПОДХОДА. In *WORLD SCIENCE: PROBLEMS AND INNOVATIONS* (pp. 156-158).

34. Narzieva, N. N. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH COMPETENCIES IN THE CONDITIONS OF INTEGRATED EDUCATION IN STUDENTS ON THE BASE OF A COMPETENT APPROACH. *Thematics Journal of Education*, 8(Q1).

35. Narzieva, N. N. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH COMPETENCES OF VETERINARY SPECIALISTS IN THE MODERNIZATION OF VETERINARY EDUCATION. *International Journal of Engineering Mathematics (Online)*, 5(3).

36. Нарзиева, Н. Н. (2022). СПОРТ ТУРЛАРИ БЎЙИЧА ТРЕНЕР-ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРИНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-МАДАНИЙ КОМПЕТЕНТЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ. *AGROBIOTEKNOLOGIYA VA VETERINARIYA TIBBIYOTI ILMIY JURNALI*, 980-983.

37. Тургунбоев, А., & Нарзиева, Н. Н. (2022). ЗАРДЎШТИЙЛИКНИНГ ТАЪЛИМ-ТАРБИЯ МАНБАИ-“АВЕСТО” ДАГИ ВЕТЕРИНАРИЯ ВА ЧОРВАЧИЛИК ТАЛҚИНИ. *AGROBIOTEKNOLOGIYA VA VETERINARIYA TIBBIYOTI ILMIY JURNALI*, 1180-1183.

38. Narzieva, N., Namazova, U., & Ernazarov, T. (2022). FACTORS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE OF HISTORY TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (5), 171-173.

39. Рахимов, Б. Х., & Нарзиева, Н. Н. (2016). ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ПОДХОДА К ОБУЧЕНИЮ. In *Образование через всю жизнь: непрерывное образование в интересах устойчивого развития* (pp. 356-360).

40. Назарова, Б., Нарзиева, Н., Умаров, Х., Машарипов, К., & Кулахметова, М. (2011). ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ПРОЦЕСС ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ НАУЧНОГО МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ. *Педагогические науки*, (1), 147-151.

41. Нарзиева, Н. Н., & Гаппарович, Х. А. ТАЯНЧ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯЛАР АСОСИДА ЎҚУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ИЗЛАНИШ, ТАДҚИҚОТ МАДАНИЯТИНИ БОСҚИЧМА-БОСҚИЧ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ. *НАМАНГАН ДАВЛАТ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ-2021*, 1, 528.

42. Davlatov, R. B., & Khushnazarov, A. K. (2024). Diagnosis and chemoprophylaxis of rabbit eumeriosis. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 480, p. 03020). EDP Sciences.

43. Раимкулов, И., Хушназаров, А., & Эшкораев, А. (2023). Способы кормления кроликов в современных клетках. *in Library*, 1(1), 52-57.

44. Эшкораев, А., Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Развитие, эпизоотология, лечение и профилактика эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(1), 65-71.

45. Раимкулов, И., Хушназаров, А., Эшкораев, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Химиопрофилактика эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(1), 56-62.

46. Расулов, У., Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Диагностика и эпизоотология эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(2), 366-368.

47. Khudoyberdievich, K. A., Khushnazarova, M. I., & Isokulova, Z. X. (2022). PREVALENCE, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF RABBIT EMERIOSIS. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 1(9), 245-249.

48. Давлатов, Р. Б., & Хушназаров, А. Х. (2022). ҚУЁН ЭЙМЕРИОЗИ ЭПИЗОТОЛОГИЯСИ ДАВОЛАШ ВА ПРОФИЛАКТИКА ЧОРА-ТАДБИРЛАРИ. *AGROBIOTEKNOLOGIYA VA VETERINARIYA TIBBIYOTI ILMIY JURNALI*, 181-184.

49. Berdiyevich, D. R., Khudoyberdi o'g'li, K. A., & Ilhomovna, K. M. (2022). EPIZOOTOLOGY OF EIMERIOSIS (COCCIDIOSIS) OF RABBITS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES. *Ann. For. Res*, 65(1), 602-607.

50. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2022). Quyon eumeriozini davolashda vazuril preparatining samaradorligi. *Library*, 22(2), 173-174.

51. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2022). Пастдарғом ва ургут туманларида қуён эймериозининг эпизоотик ҳолати. *Library*, 22(1), 31-32.
52. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2022). Қуён эймериозини даволашда янги эймериостатикнинг самарадорлиги. *Library*, 22(1), 28-29.
53. Давлатов, Р., & Хушназаров, А. (2022). Epizootology of eimeriosis (coccidiosis) of rabbits, treatment and preventive measures. *Library*, 22(4), 15.
54. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2022). Эффективность вазурила при лечении эймериоза кролика. in *Library*, 22(2), 173-174.
55. Davlatov, R. B., & Khushnazarov, A. X. (2022). TREATMENT AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES OF THE EPISOTOLOGY OF RABBIT EMERIOSIS. *SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF AGROBIOTECHNOLOGY AND VETERINARY MEDICINE*, 181-184.
56. Давлатов, Р., & Хушназаров, А. (2022). Эпизотология эймериоза (кокцидоза) кроликов, лечение и профилактика. in *Library*, 22(4).
57. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2022). Эпизототическая ситуация по эмериозу кролика в пастдаргомском и ургутском районах. in *Library*, 22(1), 31-32.
58. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2022). Эффективность нового эймериостатического препарата в лечении эймериоза кроликов. in *Library*, 22(1), 28-29.
59. Khushnazarov, A., & Davlatov, R. B. (2022). Rabbit eimeriozin in treatment vazuril of the drug efficiency. *Library*, 22(2), 173-174.
60. Хушназаров, А. Х. (2022). ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫХ ДАННЫХ ПО ХИМИОТЕРАПИИ И ХИМИОПРОФИЛАКТИКИ ЭЙМЕРИОЗА КРОЛИКОВ. *PEDAGOGS journali*, 23(2), 83-86.
61. Худойбердиевич, Х. А., Хушназарова, М. И., & Исоқулова, З. Х. (2022). ҚУЁН ЭЙМЕРИОЗИНИНГ ТАРҚАЛИШИ, ДИАГНОЗИ, ДАВОЛАШ ВА ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШ. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 1(9), 245-249.
62. Хушназаров, А., Хабибулаев, С. Л., Рахматова, У., Орлова, Г. И., Толибова, Ф. Т., & Хушназарова, М. И. (2022). Защита кроликоферм от эймериоза. in *Library*, 22(2), 5-8.
63. Хушназаров, А., Хабибулаев, С. Л., Рахматова, У., Орлова, Г. И., Толибова, Ф. Т., & Хушназарова, М. И. (2022). Защита кроликоферм от эймериоза. in *Library*, 22(2), 5-8.
64. Khushnazarov, A. X. (2022). OBZOR LITERATURNYX DANNYX PO KHIMIOTERAPII I KHIMIOPROPHYLAKTIKI EYMEROZA KROLIKOV. *Journal of PEDAGOGS*, 23(2), 83-86.
65. Урокова, М., Акрамова, М., & Хушназаров, А. Х. (2021). Эффективные методы лечения эмериоза у кроликов. in *Library*, 21(2), 115-117.
66. Хушназаров, А., Урокова, М., & Курбонова, М. (2021). Защитим кроликов от эймерий. in *Library*, 21(1), 44-47.
67. Хушназаров, А. Х., Урокова, М., & Курбонова, М. И. (2021). Quyonlar eumeriozi va uni oldini olish. *Library*, 21(2), 126-129.

68. Хушназаров, А., Урокова, М., & Курбонова, М. (2021). Защитим кроликов от эймерий. *in Library*, 21(1), 44-47.
69. Хушназаров, А. Х., Урокова, М., & Курбонова, М. И. (2021). Rabbits are eimeriosis and its prevention. *Library*, 21(2), 126-129.
70. Uroкова, М., Акрамова, М., & Khushnazarov, А. Х. (2021). Rabbits eimeriozin of treatment efficient methods. *Library*, 21(2), 115-117.
71. Урокова, М., Акрамова, М., & Хушназаров, А. Х. (2021). Эффективные методы лечения эмериоза у кроликов. *in Library*, 21(2), 115-117.
72. Хушназаров, А. Х., Урокова, М., & Курбонова, М. И. (2021). Эмериоз кроликов и его профилактика. *in Library*, 21(2), 126-129.
73. Khushnazarov, А., Uroкова, М., & Kurbonova, М. (2021). Kuyonlarni emeriozdan asraylik. *Library*, 21(1), 44-47.
74. Khushnazarov, А., Uroкова, М., & Kurbonova, М. (2021). Kuyonlarni emeriozdan asraylik. *Library*, 21(1), 44-47.
75. Избасаров, У., Турдиев, А., Дускулов, В., & Хушназаров, А. (2021). Санитарно-гигиеническая оценка полов в животноводческих помещениях в условиях жаркого климата. *in Library*, 21(1), 214-217.
76. Izbasarov, U., Turdiev, A., Duskulov, V., & Khushnazarov, A. (2021). Sanitary and hygienic assessment of floors in livestock buildings in a hot climate. *Library*, 21(1), 214-217.